

Arousal

Arousal is a measure of excitement versus calmness. A word is AROUSING if it makes you feel stimulated, excited, frenzied, jittery, or wide-awake. A word is UNAROUSING if it makes you feel relaxed, calm, sluggish, dull, or sleepy.

Please indicate how arousing you think word "X" is on a scale of 1 (VERY UNAROUSING) to 9 (VERY AROUSING), with the midpoint representing moderate arousal. Please answer only with the number.

Valence

Valence is a measure of value or worth. A word is POSITIVE if it represents something considered good, whereas a word is NEGATIVE if it represents something considered bad.

Please indicate the valence of word "X" on a scale of 1 (VERY NEGATIVE) to 9 (VERY POSITIVE), with the midpoint representing NEUTRAL. Please answer only with the number.

Dominance

Dominance is a measure of the degree of control you feel. A word can make you feel DOMINANT, influential, in control, important, or autonomous. Conversely, a word can make you feel CONTROLLED, influenced, cared-for, submissive, or guided. Please answer only with the number.

Please indicate how word "X" make you feel on a scale of 1 (YOU ARE VERY CONTROLLED) to 9 (YOU ARE VERY DOMINANT), with the midpoint being neither controlled nor dominant. Please answer only with the number.

Concreteness

Concreteness is a measure of how concrete or abstract something is. A word is CONCRETE if it represents something that exists in a definite physical form in the real world. In contrast, a word is ABSTRACT if it represents more of a concept or idea. Please answer only with the number.

Please indicate how concrete you think word "X" is on a scale of 1 (VERY ABSTRACT) to 7 (VERY CONCRETE), with the midpoint being neither especially abstract nor concrete. Please answer only with the number.

Imageability

Imageability is a measure of how easy or difficult something is to imagine. A word is IMAGEABLE if it represents something that is very easy to imagine or picture. In contrast, a word is UNIMAGEABLE if it represents something that is very difficult to imagine or picture.

Please indicate how imageable you think word "X" is on a scale of 1 (VERY UNIMAGEABLE) to 7 (VERY IMAGEABLE), with the midpoint being moderately imageable. Please answer only with the number.

Familiarity

Familiarity is a measure of how familiar something is. A word is very FAMILIAR if you see/hear it often and it is easily recognisable. In contrast, a word is very UNFAMILIAR if you rarely see/hear it and it is relatively unrecognisable.

Please indicate how familiar you think word “X” is on a scale of 1 (VERY UNFAMILIAR) to 7 (VERY FAMILIAR), with the midpoint representing moderate familiarity. Please answer only with the number.

Gender

A word’s gender is how strongly its meaning is associated with male or female behaviour. A word can be considered MASCULINE if it is linked to male behaviour. Alternatively, a word can be considered FEMININE if it is linked to female behaviour.

Please indicate the gender associated with word “X” on a scale of 1 (VERY FEMININE) to 7 (VERY MASCULINE), with the midpoint being neuter (neither feminine nor masculine). Please answer only with the number.